

Oxidation Studies. Part VI*

Kinetics of Oxidation of Some Amino Acids by Ce^{4+} in H_2SO_4 Medium in the Presence and Absence of Ag^+

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Kinetics of oxidation of amino acids viz., serine, threonine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid were studied in presence and absence of Ag^+ . Glycine and α -alanine were oxidised only in the presence of Ag^+ . In the absence of Ag^+ the order of $[Ce^{4+}]$ and $[amino\ acid]$ were found to be one each and the mechanism is explained by a straightforward bimolecular reaction between Ce^{4+} and amino acid. In the presence of Ag^+ , the order of $[Ce^{4+}]$ was found to be unity and that of $[amino\ acid]$ and $[Ag^+]$ were fractional. The observed rate law was explained by assuming the formation of an adduct between amino acid and Ag^+ in a fast step. This adduct was assumed to react with Ce^{4+} in the rate determining step to yield Ag^{2+} -substrate adduct which ultimately undergoes internal oxidation in a fast step to give the products. The formation constants of the adduct (K) and bimolecular rate constants for the slow step (k) at different temperatures and other activation parameters are presented and discussed.

A g^+ catalysis of Ce^{4+} oxidations was first observed by Sinha¹. Later in our laboratory² it was shown that Ag^+ acts as a good catalyst in the oxidation of a variety of organic substrates by ceric sulphate. The literature survey shows that not much work has been done on the kinetics of oxidation of amino acids by ceric sulphate. Recently it was reported³ that glycine was not appreciably affected by ceric sulphate. It was reported⁴ by us that acetic acid which is not oxidised even under reflux condition by Ce^{4+} in H_2SO_4 gets oxidised when Ce^{4+} - Ag^+ system was used. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to employ this system for the oxidation of glycine and α -alanine which do not react with Ce^{4+} in the absence of Ag^+ . For comparison purpose other amino acids such as serine, threonine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid which react both in the absence and presence of Ag^+ were studied

rate constants (k') were calculated from the slope of the plot of $\log \frac{a}{a-x}$ vs time. The rate of oxidation

of serine, threonine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid show a first order dependence on the $[amino\ acid]$ in the absence of Ag^+ as was observed from the slope of the plot of $\log k'$ vs $\log [amino\ acid]$. However, in the presence of Ag^+ the order of $[amino\ acid]$ changed from unity to fractional (the order of serine, threonine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid being 0.45, 0.48, 0.40 and 0.50 respectively). Increase in concentration of Ag^+ increased the rate and the order of $[Ag^+]$ was also found to be fractional (order of Ag^+ in the oxidation of serine, threonine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid were 0.7, 0.65, 0.6 and 0.62 respectively). The effect of $[Ag^+]$ on k' in Ce^{4+} -threonine or glutamic acid reactions as typical examples are given in Table 1. The concentration of Ag^+ was

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH (AR) grade. Amino acids were either Fluka or BDH Biochemicals. The method of following the kinetics was same as in our earlier paper⁵. Ammonia, carbon dioxide and corresponding aldehyde⁶ were identified as the products during the oxidation of all these amino acids.

Results

Serine, threonine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid react with Ce^{4+} in the absence of Ag^+ , whereas glycine and α -alanine do not. Under conditions of $[Ce^{4+}] \ll [amino\ acid]$ the order of $[Ce^{4+}]$ was found to be unity in all the cases. The pseudo-first order

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF $[Ag^+]$ ON k' IN Ce^{4+} -THREONINE OR GLUTAMIC ACID REACTION

$[Ag^+]$ mol l ⁻¹	$k' \times 10^4$ min ⁻¹	
	Threonine	Glutamic acid
0.00	1.07	1.12
0.01	99.0	33.4
0.02	138.0	51.0
0.03	173.0	64.0
0.04	230.0	85.0
0.05	288.0	94.0
0.06	345.0	102.0
0.07	397.0	115.0

$[Threonine] = 0.020M$;

Temp. = 55°

$[Glutamic\ acid] = 0.025M$;

Temp. = 60°.

$[Ce^{4+}] = 1.50 \times 10^{-3}M$

$[H_2SO_4] = 1.0M$

$\mu = 2.59M$

* A part of it is presented at II National Symposium on Catalysis, Kharagpur, 1975.

found to be unchanged at the end of the reaction as indicated by the constant thiocyanate titre value. Increase in $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ or $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ decreased the rate and increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ at constant ionic strength increased the rate. The activation energy values were calculated from the slope of the Arrhenius plots in the temperature range $40^\circ\text{--}65^\circ$. This as well as the other thermodynamic parameters are presented in Table 2. Addition of acrylamide to the reaction system produced in a few minutes a white gelatinous precipitate indicating the presence of free radicals.

Discussion

In the absence of Ag^+ the order of $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ and [amino acid] were found to be one each. Spectral studies, effect of SO_4^{2-} , HSO_4^- and H^+ show a similar trend to the one reported earlier⁵ for other substrates indicating that neutral $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ might be the reactive species. Since the rate law is same reported for other substrates, a similar mechanism could be operative in the case of these amino acids also. The products of oxidation were ammonia, carbon dioxide and aldehyde. This may be explained by assuming the OH bond fission to occur in the rate determining step. If however, C-H bond fission occurs the product would be entirely different.

Thus the reaction scheme for glutamic acid as a typical example could be written as follows :

Ag⁺ catalysis

In the presence of Ag^+ the order of [amino acid] changed from unity to fractional (~ 0.5) indicating

* $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ is written as Ce^{4+} for simplicity.

that it may be involved in complex formation either with Ce^{4+} or Ag^+ . Spectral studies in the present work indicated no complexation between Ce^{4+} and amino acid under the experimental conditions used in the present work. Ag^+ is known to form colourless adducts with oxygen containing compounds with lone pair of electrons on oxygen atom⁷. It is therefore not unreasonable to assume the formation of an adduct between Ag^+ and amino acid before oxidation by Ce^{4+} occurs in a slow step to yield Ag^{2+} -substrate adduct. The formation of Ag^{2+} -substrate adduct was confirmed by adding bipyridyl to the reaction system which gave brown coloured bipyridyl complex of Ag^{2+} with its characteristic absorption maximum at 454 nm.⁸ Taking the adduct formation as the first step the reaction scheme for the Ce^{4+} -glutamic acid reaction as a typical example in the presence of Ag^+ could be written as

From the above mechanism the rate equation comes out to be

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{-2.303 \, d \log [\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{dt} &= K' \\ &= \frac{Kk[\text{Ag}^+][\text{amino acid}]}{1 + K[\text{amino acid}] + K[\text{Ag}^+]} \quad \dots (I) \end{aligned}$$

where k' is the observed first order rate constant, k is the bimolecular rate constant for the slow step and K is the formation constant of the adduct. Equation (I) accounts for the first order dependence of rate on $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ and fractional order dependence on $[\text{Ag}^+]$ and [amino acid] obtained experimentally.

Taking reciprocals of the equation (I), we get

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{[\text{amino acid}]} \left[\frac{1}{Kk[\text{Ag}^+]} + \frac{1}{k} \right] + \frac{1}{k[\text{Ag}^+]} \dots \text{(II)}$$

From equation (II) it is clear that the plots of

$$\frac{1}{k'} \text{ vs } \frac{1}{[\text{amino acid}]}$$

at constant $[\text{Ag}^+]$ should be linear. Such plots were obtained in the present work for all the amino acids studied (Fig. 1). From the intercept and slope

Fig. 1. The plot of $\frac{1}{k'}$ vs $\frac{1}{[\text{glycine}]}$

$[\text{Ce}^{4+}] = 1.50 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[\text{Ag}^+] = 0.05 M$
 $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0 M$. Temperature = 65° . $\mu = 2.57 M$

values the bimolecular rate constant for the slow step (k) and formation constant for the adduct (K) were evaluated at different temperatures to calculate activation parameters.

Since all the experiments were conducted in $1.0 M$ H_2SO_4 , the amino acids exist in the reaction mixture as NH_3^+

as $\text{R}-\text{CH}-\text{COOH}$ (1). The stability of the above species increases as the difference between the isoelectric point and the pH of the reaction mixture increases. Since this difference decreases in the order aspartic acid < glutamic acid < glycine < α -alanine their ability to form the adduct with the positively charged Ag^+ increases in the order aspartic acid > glutamic acid > glycine \approx α -alanine. This is in conformity with the formation constants (K) of the adduct (table 2). Probably for the same reason the bimolecular rate constants (k) for the slow step also follow the same trend. The formation constants of serine, threonine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid and α -alanine are in the order serine > threonine > aspartic acid > glutamic acid > glycine \approx alanine. The large increase in formation constant values in case of serine and threonine might be due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding as given below :

[Structure (2) is less stable compared to structure (3) because of the electron donating nature of CH_3 group].

These neutral species (2) or (3) might form better adducts with Ag^+ than the positively charged species (1). Hence, the bimolecular rate constants (k) for serine, and threonine should also be higher than for other amino acids as observed in the present work (Table 2).

The plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger for catalysed reactions is linear with a slope equal to 355°K which is the iso-

TABLE 2

Amino acid	$k \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at 55°	ΔE^\ddagger $k \text{ cal. mol}^{-1}$	ΔH^\ddagger $k \text{ cal. mol}^{-1}$	ΔG^\ddagger $k \text{ cal. mol}^{-1}$	ΔS^\ddagger E.u.	$K \text{ lit. mol}^{-1}$
Glycine	22.2 (—)	32.04(—)	31.39(—)	23.26(—)	24.8 (—)	7.2
α -Alanine	12.5 (—)	34.33(—)	33.87(—)	23.63(—)	30.61(—)	5.9
Serine	1305.0 (1.64)	36.0 (10.7)	35.34(10.1)	20.6 (24.9)	44.9 (—45.6)	43.1
Threonine	333.4 (0.88)	19.1 (7.2)	18.4 (6.5)	21.5 (25.4)	—9.3 (57.4)	30.9
Aspartic acid	88.0 (15.99)	30.5 (18.3)	29.8 (17.7)	22.4(23.5)	22.8 (—17.5)	19.6
Glutamic acid	76.1 (1.37)	16.34(22.89)	15.68(22.34)	22.56(25.1)	—20.67(—8.3)	12.4

The values given in the parenthesis are those for the uncatalysed reaction.

kinetic temperature. The isokinetic temperature is greater than the temperature range used in the present work (313°K–338°K) indicating that the reactions are enthalpy controlled as is evident from Table 2.

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